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ENVIRONMENTAL GOVERNANCE IN ORBIT: NAVIGATING EIA AND ESG PRESSURES IN THE NEWSPACE INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

As private equity and venture capital investment in the NewSpace sector rapidly increases, investors are placing growing emphasis on Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) compliance. A key tool in assessing environmental responsibility is the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA). However, current EIA frameworks are fragmented, Earth-focused, and inadequate for evaluating the impacts of space activities. This paper examines how this regulatory gap hinders both sustainability goals and investor confidence. Drawing on legal instruments such as the Outer Space Treaty, Moon Agreement and the Long-Term Sustainability Guidelines, the paper advocates for the development of soft-law-based extraterrestrial EIA guidelines. Institutions such as the Inter-Agency Space Debris Coordination Committee (IADC) and United Nations Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (UNCOPUOS) are well placed to lead this initiative. The analysis also considers broader structural issues affecting the implementation of ESG in the space sector, including the resource limitations of space start-ups and the growing expectations of institutional investors. Considering these factors, the paper recommends the introduction of harmonised standards and soft law guidelines as a realistic and commercially viable first step.

KEYWORDS: ESG (Environment, Social, Governance), EIA (Environmental Impact Assessments), NewSpace, Venture Capital.

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1. INTRODUCTION

At the dawn of the space age in 1957, with the launch of Sputnik-1 by the USSR, there was a major push toward the development of space technologies by States across the globe. One of the key drivers for the development of space technologies was getting the technological edge over other States, and it is this reason why an international legal framework was the need of the hour. This motivation was the basis for States establishing the international law principles and the core space law frameworks. These principles are still applicable over 60 years later and continue to emphasize peace and international cooperation.² The primary international legal instrument embodying these principles is the *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and other Celestial Bodies* (Outer Space Treaty)³. Through the end of the 20th century, space activities remained primarily dominated by government entities.

This trend began to shift in the late 1990s as non-state actors became increasingly involved in space activities. While early private initiatives often relied on government support, the early twenty-first century marked a turning point with the emergence of privately driven space enterprises operating more independently.⁴ Technological advancements enabled non-state actors to develop and deploy space technologies, encouraging entrepreneurs to address operational and technological gaps within the commercial space sector. These ventures range from start-ups to established companies, and governments worldwide have responded by introducing regulatory frameworks to promote entrepreneurship and expand access to space. As a result, commercial investment in space operations has grown significantly. There has been a steady growth of private equity and venture capital firms backing NewSpace companies, and in the five years from 2018 to 2023, commercial investments within the space sector increased by 22% annually.⁵ Since 2019, 234 different lead investors have led 347 deals in the European NewSpace sector alone. Most of the investment volume was led by the private sector, consisting of 67.3%.⁶ This shows that NewSpace companies are increasingly and majorly backed by private investors. On one hand, this opens a lot of opportunities for NewSpace companies in terms of access to the global financial market, access to diverse forms of capital investments, etc. However, it also raises the important question of increased scrutiny when it comes to Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) compliance.

In recent years, there has been an increasing focus on ESG compliance when evaluating investment opportunities. However, in the context of venture capital, many start-ups are still in the early stages of development and often lack the capacity or resources to adequately address ESG issues, and this holds true for the NewSpace industry as well. Many venture capital funds are placing greater emphasis on ESG criteria to differentiate themselves as long-term, reliable partners for responsible investing focused on sustainability. These venture capital funds also have to satisfy the sustainability-linked “green” requirements of their limited partners or parent investors, thereby triggering this increased scrutiny of

² Schneider, S. (2025). 54: NewSpace and the law. In *Elgar concise encyclopedia of space law*. Edward Elgar Publishing.

³ United Nations. (1967). *Treaty on principles governing the activities of states in the exploration and use of outer space, including the moon and other celestial bodies* (610 U.N.T.S. 205). <https://treaties.un.org/Pages/showDetails.aspx?objid=0800000280025899>.

⁴ Ibid.

⁵ Sandhu, N., Harrington, J., & Klein, J. (2023, July 20). *R & D for space: Who is actually funding it?* McKinsey & Company. <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/aerospace-and-defense/our-insights/r-and-d-for-space-who-is-actually-funding-it>.

⁶ European Space Policy Institute. (2024, March). *Bridging the financing gap in the European space sector: Facts & figures*. <https://www.espi.or.at/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/ESPI-Facts-Figures-Bridging-the-Financing-Gap-in-the-European-Space-Sector.pdf>.

ESG criteria while making investments.⁷ This leads to additional compliance costs for NewSpace start-ups, operating in cutting-edge frontier technologies with limited resources and often leads to incomplete compliance or not meeting the required “sustainability” threshold and therefore critically reducing the access to financial markets for NewSpace companies. The current paper seeks to explore this by examining the evolution of ESG principles within venture capital and private equity funds and their application in high-growth, innovation-driven industries such as NewSpace. It will then assess how these factors impact the NewSpace industry by looking at private investment trends and their respective ESG criteria. The second half of the paper will address the legal challenges that arise for NewSpace companies, including compliance with fragmented or underdeveloped regulatory frameworks, specifically with regard to ESG compliance and sustainability obligations. Finally, the paper will offer observations on how emerging companies can navigate these challenges through the evolution of a uniform framework to better support ESG-conscious investment in the space sector. It contends that soft law instruments developed through international coordination bodies such as the United Nations Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (UNCOPUOS) or Inter-Agency Space Debris Coordination Committee (IADC) represent the most feasible pathway for the development of extraterrestrial EIA standards. Therefore, this paper asks: To what extent can Environmental Impact Assessments be adapted to regulate environmental impacts in outer space, and how can such frameworks support ESG-driven investment in the NewSpace industry?

2. RISE OF ESG INVESTING IN VENTURE CAPITAL AND NEWSPACE

In recent years, investors have increasingly prioritized Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) considerations, evaluating not only the profits companies generate but also the manner in which those profits are achieved. This growing interest is supported by market research indicating that, as of early 2018, global sustainable investment assets had reached USD 30.7 trillion – an increase of 34% since 2016 – with Europe representing the largest share of these assets. Additionally, the most recent figures show that more than 3,000 organisations worldwide have become signatories to the United Nations’ Principles for Responsible Investment (UN PRI).⁸ This is also in line with the broader EU Green Deal objectives, wherein the European Commission seeks to (i) reorient capital flows toward more sustainable investments, (ii) manage sustainability risks, and (iii) improve transparency. For the past few years, investors have developed and refined their appetite for sustainable investments. Many investors have shifted from a traditional two-dimensional “risk/return analysis” to a three-dimensional “risk/return/sustainability analysis”. The *Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation (SFDR)*⁹ in the EU has contributed to this phenomenon. For example, the European Investment Fund (EIF) has committed EUR 5.64 billion in equity, including private equity, venture capital and debt finance, for investments that align with the UN Sustainable Development Goals.¹⁰ This points to a gradual and widespread shift taking place across the globe, and in Europe, where investors are keen to invest in projects that align with sustainability goals.

⁷ Bird & Bird. (2022, July 13). *The role of ESG considerations in venture capital investments*. <https://www.twobirds.com/en/insights/2022/global/the-role-of-esg-considerations-in-venture-capital-investments>.

⁸ Botsari, A., & Lang, F. (2020, June). *ESG considerations in venture capital and business angel investment decisions: Evidence from two pan-European surveys* (EIF Working Paper No. 2020/63). European Investment Fund. https://www.eif.org/news_centre/publications/EIF_Working_Paper_2020_63.html.

⁹ European Parliament & Council of the European Union. (2019). *Regulation (EU) 2019/2088 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 November 2019 on sustainability-related disclosures in the financial services sector* (OJ L 317, 9.12.2019, p. 1). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32019R2088>.

¹⁰ EY. (2023, May 9). *SFDR funds: The power of voluntary assurance*. https://www.ey.com/en_lu/insights/wealth-asset-management/sfdr-funds-the-power-of-voluntary-assurance.

Applying this evolving emphasis on ESG considerations to the NewSpace sector, which is predominantly financed through private equity and venture capital, highlights a significant shift in investment dynamics. As ESG factors become integral to investment decisions, NewSpace companies must align their operations and product designs with sustainability criteria to attract and retain funding. This alignment is not merely a compliance exercise but a strategic imperative, as investors increasingly view robust ESG practices as indicators of long-term viability and risk mitigation. Consequently, NewSpace enterprises are encouraged to integrate ESG principles into their core strategies, ensuring that their innovations contribute positively to environmental and social objectives, thereby meeting the heightened expectations of contemporary investors. Another key aspect of NewSpace companies is that they are often founded by engineers or space enthusiasts who seek to develop new products and services from scratch and require extensive testing, certifications, and resources.¹¹ This can sometimes also translate to many startups lacking the relevant expertise or resources to develop comprehensive ESG strategies. Additionally, the absence of standardized ESG metrics and reporting frameworks can make it difficult for companies to demonstrate their ESG performance effectively. These factors can act as barriers to securing investment, as investors may perceive higher risks or question the company's long-term viability.¹²

3. ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT ASSESSMENTS IN NEWSPACE

3.1. Environmental Concerns

Space exploration is a polluting industry;¹³ its environmental impact on the outer space environment and the Earth varies depending on the nature and phase of the activity. Launching a space object raises different environmental issues than extracting resources from a celestial body. In the space industry, there exist two broad forms of contamination, forward contamination and backward contamination. Forward contamination refers to the introduction of terrestrial material into the outer space environment and onto other celestial bodies, such as the Moon, Mars or asteroids. For example, when landing on celestial bodies, it is impossible to ensure the complete absence of chemical and radiological contamination. Rocket exhaust, gas release from activities, and astronauts' life support systems inevitably release chemicals into the outer space environment. By contrast, backward contamination refers to the risks associated with introducing extraterrestrial materials into the Earth's environment.¹⁴ This is also where Article IX of the Outer Space Treaty comes into effect, where state parties are required to conduct all their activities in outer space with due regard to the corresponding interests of all other state parties, and parties must avoid harmful contamination of outer space as well as prevent adverse changes in the environment of the earth, resulting from the introduction of extra-terrestrial matter and, where necessary shall adopt appropriate measures for this purpose.¹⁵ In addition to Article IX of the Outer Space Treaty, Article 7 of the *Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies* (Moon Agreement)¹⁶ provides that all State parties must take measures to prevent the disruption of the existing balance of its environment, whether by introducing adverse changes in that environment or by its harmful

¹¹ Hameed, H., & Veneziano, A. (2023). The Space Protocol of the Cape Town Convention: A tool to promote greater commercialisation and private financing in the space sector. In P. De Man (Ed.), *Routledge handbook of commercial space law* (p. 88). Routledge.

¹² Bird & Bird, *supra* note 7.

¹³ Ahuja, V. (2015). Space activities and environmental pollution. In V. S. Mani, B. Bhatt, & V. Balakista Reddy (Eds.), *Recent trends in international space law and policy*. Lancers Books.

¹⁴ Leterre, G. (2023). Environmental protection. In F. von der Dunk (Ed.), *Elgar concise encyclopedia of space law* (p. 88). Edward Elgar Publishing.

¹⁵ United Nations. (1967). *Treaty on principles governing the activities of states in the exploration and use of outer space, including the moon and other celestial bodies* (610 U.N.T.S. 205), art. IX. <https://treaties.un.org/Pages/showDetails.aspx?objid=0800000280128cbd>.

¹⁶ United Nations. (1979). *Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies*. https://www.unoosa.org/pdf/gares/ARES_34_68E.pdf.

contamination through the introduction of extra-terrestrial matter.¹⁷ That said, it is important to note that the Moon Agreement has 17 signatories and has not been ratified by any state capable of human spaceflight; therefore, it has little relevance in international space law.¹⁸

A contemporary example illustrating the environmental implications of space activities is the rapid deployment of large satellite constellations in low Earth orbit. Companies developing global broadband networks plan to launch thousands of satellites, significantly increasing the density of objects in orbit. This raises concerns related to space debris generation, collision risks, and the long-term sustainability of the orbital environment. The cumulative environmental impact of such constellations demonstrates the need for systematic environmental assessments capable of evaluating both terrestrial and orbital consequences of space missions.¹⁹

However, over the past decades, space activities have largely been governed by soft law instruments, including initiatives such as the Artemis Accords,²⁰ the UNCOPUOS Long Term Sustainability Guidelines (LTS Guidelines),²¹ and the Space Debris Mitigation Guidelines developed by the IADC.²² These voluntary instruments, of course, do not have the same binding value as an international treaty, but are seeing an increased usage, specifically with regard to sustainability. These soft law instruments can take several forms, such as declarations, principles, standards or guidelines. Several non-legally binding instruments have been adopted to mitigate space debris. In 2002, IADC adopted space debris mitigation standards addressed to space operators. Likewise, the UNCOPUOS adopted in 2007 its own voluntary guidelines to help states and international organisations in the space debris mitigation process. Although these guidelines are voluntary, it can be noted that several states have implemented them in their domestic legal system.²³ As States have the power to voluntarily enforce soft law instruments, they become binding upon governmental and non-governmental entities operating within the space sector. For example, several states have decided to make space debris mitigation measures a requirement for authorisation to conduct space activities, and for some states, the national legislation requires compliance with international standards and guidelines.²⁴

3.2. Evolutions Of Environmental Impact Assessments in Space Governance

Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) requirements and licensing regulations are critical components of the space industry's regulatory framework, ensuring that space activities are conducted responsibly and sustainably. These requirements vary across jurisdictions but generally aim to assess and mitigate the environmental impacts of space operations. However, EIA have existed for a considerable period. One of the earliest instances of mandatory EIA procedures in the United States can be traced back to the 1969

¹⁷ United Nations. (1979). *Agreement governing the activities of states on the moon and other celestial bodies* (1363 U.N.T.S. 3), art. 7. <https://treaties.un.org/doc/Publication/UNTS/Volume%201363/volume-1363-I-23002-English.pdf>.

¹⁸ Tronchetti, F. (2024). Moon Agreement: Key provisions. In F. Tronchetti & S. Freeland (Eds.), *International space law in the new space era*. Oxford University Press.

¹⁹ McDowell, J. (2020). The Low Earth Orbit Satellite Population and Impacts of the Starlink Constellation. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters*. <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.3847/2041-8213/ab8016>

²⁰ National Aeronautics and Space Administration. (2020). Artemis Accords: Principles for cooperation in the civil exploration and use of the Moon, Mars, comets, and asteroids (Version 1.0). <https://www.nasa.gov/office/spacepolicy/accords>.

²¹ United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. (2021). Guidelines for the long-term sustainability of outer space activities of the Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space. United Nations. https://www.unoosa.org/documents/pdf/PromotingSpaceSustainability/Publication_Final_English_June2021.pdf.

²² Inter-Agency Space Debris Coordination Committee. (2007). IADC space debris mitigation guidelines. https://www.iadc-home.org/documents_public/view/id/97.

²³ Leterre, *supra* note 14.

²⁴ *Ibid*.

National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA).²⁵ This act followed from the historic US vs. Canada *Trail Smelter Arbitration*, where obligations under international environmental law that required EIAs were first introduced.²⁶ In the decades that followed, international jurisprudence further developed these principles. For instance, in the *Gabcikovo-Nagymaros case*, the International Court of Justice (ICJ) found a duty to conduct EIAs before proceeding with serious transboundary projects under customary international law as well as treaty and customary obligations to consult and cooperate in the implementation of projects which might affect other states' interests.²⁷ Thereafter, EIAs have been a successful tool to mitigate and understand the environmental impact of developmental activities. However, despite its success in other fields, environmental impact assessment is not a well-established tool in the international law of outer space. As noted *infra*, the national legislation of some spacefaring countries requires an EIA to be conducted for space activities.²⁸ According to Section 11 of the *2018 Space Industry Act* (United Kingdom), the applicant seeking permission to conduct space activities must submit an assessment of environmental effects. This is an assessment of the effect that launches from the spaceport are expected to have on the environment. It should cover air quality, emissions targets, biodiversity, marine impacts, noise pollution, etc.²⁹ Further, the European Space Agency (ESA) conducts Life Cycle Assessments (LCAs) rather than EIAs for its missions, and ESA's clean space initiative has developed guidelines to support this process.³⁰ However, the guidelines state that the LCA methodology has been developed to quantify environmental impacts on the Earth's ecosphere and, therefore, impacts to the extraterrestrial environment are presumably excluded from consideration. The LCA studies performed by ESA to date have focused on spacecraft and launchers and have identified the environmental impact in terms of environmental indicators, such as global warming potential, ozone depletion potential, etc.³¹

The current landscape of EIA requirements in the space sector reveals a fragmented and inconsistent approach across jurisdictions, with most regulations primarily focused on terrestrial environmental impacts. While countries like the United States, through NEPA, and the United Kingdom, via Section 11 of the 2018 Space Industry Act, mandate environmental assessments as part of their space activity licensing regimes, these typically address conventional indicators, such as air quality, emissions, biodiversity, and noise pollution, concerns rooted firmly in Earth-based ecosystems. Similarly, the European Space Agency's use of LCAs under its Clean Space initiative, though commendable, is limited to assessing environmental burdens on Earth, explicitly excluding extraterrestrial environments from consideration. This creates a regulatory blind spot, as the cumulative impacts of orbital debris, surface contamination, and resource extraction on celestial bodies remain largely ungoverned. Without a standardized, globally recognised EIA framework that incorporates the protection of the outer space environment, claims of sustainability in the NewSpace sector remain incomplete. For investors

²⁵ National Environmental Policy Act of 1969, Pub. L. No. 91-190, 83 Stat. 852 (1969). <https://www.govinfo.gov/content/pkg/STATUTE-83/pdf/STATUTE-83-Pg852.pdf>.

²⁶ United States v. Canada, *Trail Smelter Arbitration* (1938, 1941) 3 R.I.A.A. 1905. https://legal.un.org/riaa/cases/vol_III/1905-1982.pdf.

²⁷ Court of Justice. (1997). *Case concerning the Gabcikovo-Nagymaros Project (Hungary/Slovakia)*, I.C.J. Reports 1997, p. 7. <https://www.icj-cij.org/case/92>.

²⁸ Viikari, L., Escobedo, R., Suomalainen, K., Drolshagen, G., & Lehr, C. (2004). Environmental impact assessment and space activities. *Advances in Space Research*, 34(11), 2363–2369. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/234520430_Environmental_Impact_Assessment_and_Space_Activities.

²⁹ Stevens & Bolton LLP. (2023, April 4). *UK space law: The Space Industry Act 2018 and regulations*. <https://www.stevens-bolton.com/insights/102ljzu/uk-space-law-the-space-industry-act-2018-and-regulations-key-provisions-for-sp/>.

³⁰ European Space Agency. (2016). *Space system life cycle assessment (LCA) guidelines* (ESA LCA Working Group). European Space Agency.

³¹ Morozova, E., & Pozdnakova, M. (2018). Sustainability in outer space: Legal framework and current practices. *The International Journal of Marine and Coastal Law*, 21(3), 496–518. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14615517.2018.1500092>.

increasingly guided by ESG criteria and sustainability mandates, this regulatory gap poses a reputational and operational risk, potentially deterring capital flows into space ventures that cannot credibly demonstrate their environmental responsibility beyond Earth.

3.3. Establishing the Need for Extraterrestrial EIA

As NewSpace enterprises increasingly venture into advanced activities such as in-orbit servicing, asteroid mining, and lunar exploration, they are required to comply with legal obligations under international space law. For example, Article IX of the Outer Space Treaty (OST) mandates that states avoid harmful contamination of celestial bodies and conduct activities with due regard to the interests of other states. However, the current global framework for EIAs in space activities is fragmented and primarily Earth-centric, lacking comprehensive provisions for assessing impacts on extraterrestrial environments.³² This regulatory gap poses risks for NewSpace companies, as non-compliance with international obligations could lead to legal challenges. Furthermore, it is now a common and established practice for investors to increasingly prioritize ESG considerations, and the absence of robust extraterrestrial environmental safeguards may deter investment in space ventures. Therefore, establishing clear, internationally recognized EIA protocols that encompass extraterrestrial impacts is crucial for ensuring legal compliance, promoting sustainable space activities, and attracting responsible investment.

Despite the fragmented EIA requirements, two areas of extra-terrestrial environmental protection have been taken more seriously by the international community: space debris mitigation and planetary protection. But other issues of similar importance have been given far less attention. For example, potential contamination by radioactive material, which is often used by landers and spacecrafts³³ has received comparatively limited attention. Radioisotope power systems are widely used in deep space missions to provide electrical power and thermal regulation where solar energy is insufficient. These systems rely on radioactive isotopes such as plutonium-238 to generate heat. Another unexplored issue concerns the protection of environmental resources on celestial bodies. Research highlighted by Prof. Irmgard Ehrenfreund emphasizes that unregulated extraction or contamination of such resources could irreversibly damage scientifically valuable environments or disrupt future exploration efforts. The absence of clear environmental safeguards for activities such as resource extraction, infrastructure construction, or waste disposal on celestial bodies highlights a significant gap in the current regulatory framework.³⁴ In order to achieve a more uniform, comprehensive and inclusive extraterrestrial EIA framework, there are a few technical barriers which need to be addressed⁶ such as how to screen and scope EIAs to ensure that any drastic effects on the extraterrestrial environment are assessed, and are not within the scope of this paper.³⁵ However, hypothetically assuming that these technical barriers have been addressed, better norms for the protection of outer space are an imperative need as States as well as non-state actors increasingly exploit outer space. The amount of pollution and debris that is being generated impairs present and future space activities.³⁶

The author is of the view that soft law instruments have been more effective than binding treaty law in advancing sustainability in outer space. Instruments such as the IADC Space Debris Mitigation

³² National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine. (2018). *Environmental assessment for space missions: Proceedings of a workshop*. National Academies Press. <https://nap.nationalacademies.org/read/25172/chapter/4>.

³³ Lyall, F. (2010). Planetary protection from a legal perspective – General issues. In M. Hoffman, P. Rettberg, & M. Williamson (Eds.), *IAA cosmic study 2010: Protecting the environment of celestial bodies* (pp.55–62). International Academy of Astronautics.

³⁴ Ehrenfreund, P., Race, M., & Labdon, D. (2013). Responsible Space Exploration and Use: Balancing Stakeholder Interests. New Space. <https://doi.org/10.1089/space.2013.0007>.

³⁵ Morozova and Pozdnakova, *supra* note 31.

³⁶ Gupta, V. (2016). Critique of the international law on protection of the outer space environment. *Astropolitics: The International Journal of Space Politics & Policy*, 14(1), 20–43. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14777622.2016.1148462>.

Guidelines and the UN Long-Term Sustainability Guidelines for Outer Space Activities, despite their non-binding nature, have influenced a growing number of national space laws, demonstrating how soft law coupled with an urgent regulatory need can work in our favour. For example, France and Belgium have taken preliminary steps by referencing extraterrestrial environmental impact assessment requirements in their national legislation. Yet, such instances remain rare, isolated, and lacking in harmonization, leading to many commercial actors falling short of meeting consistent sustainability benchmarks.³⁷

To overcome the current patchwork of regulations, organizations like the IADC are in a strong position to lead the way in shaping soft law guidelines for extraterrestrial EIAs. Just as their work on space debris mitigation has been widely embraced by national space agencies, similar guidance on EIAs could offer a practical foundation for countries to build on. This approach would help bring consistency and clarity to how space activities are assessed for environmental impact, creating a more coordinated and reliable framework. Ultimately, it would support not just the sustainability of space operations today but also safeguard the extraterrestrial environment for the generations that will follow.³⁸

4. CONCLUSION

The NewSpace sector is experiencing an unprecedented surge in private equity and venture capital investment, driven by technological advancements and the growing commercial viability of space-based services. As this industry matures, investors are no longer focused solely on innovation and profitability; they are increasingly aligning their portfolios with ESG principles, seeking ventures that demonstrate responsible practices and long-term sustainability. One of the principal tools that investors use to assess environmental responsibility is the EIA, which helps to identify and mitigate the environmental risks associated with a company's activities.

Existing legal instruments, such as the Outer Space Treaty, recognise the importance of preventing harmful contamination and protecting the space environment, yet they provide limited guidance on how environmental impacts should be assessed in practice. While certain national licensing regimes incorporate environmental review processes, these mechanisms rarely extend to the protection of extraterrestrial environments or the cumulative impacts of space activities. As commercial actors increasingly engage in activities such as satellite mega-constellations, lunar exploration, and potential resource extraction, this regulatory gap becomes increasingly significant. In this context, the development of extraterrestrial EIA frameworks could serve as a practical tool for operationalising environmental governance in space. Importantly, such mechanisms would also help address investor concerns related to ESG compliance, enabling NewSpace companies to demonstrate that their activities align with emerging sustainability expectations.

However, as this paper has demonstrated, the current EIA frameworks applicable to the space sector are fragmented, inconsistent, and largely Earth-centric. While some jurisdictions, such as France and Belgium, have taken early steps to incorporate environmental assessments into their space licensing regimes, these efforts remain rare and lack harmonisation. As a result, the true objective of sustainability, particularly in relation to the extraterrestrial environment, remains unfulfilled. Without a unified and comprehensive approach to EIAs that extends beyond Earth's ecosystem, investors face difficulty in accurately evaluating the environmental impact of space ventures. This uncertainty can reduce investment confidence and limit access to capital for otherwise promising NewSpace companies. To address this

³⁷ Mustow, S. E. (2018). Environmental impact assessment (EIA) screening and scoping of extraterrestrial exploration and development projects. *Impact Assessment and Project Appraisal*, 36(6), 467–478. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14615517.2018.1500092>.

³⁸ Smith, L. J. (2017). *National licensing practices and regulation of private sector involvement in space*. Secure World Foundation. https://swfound.org/media/50897/smith_nationallicensing.pdf.

regulatory gap, the international community have to develop a more coherent and standardised framework for conducting EIAs for space activities, including their potential impacts on extraterrestrial environments. Such a framework, most realistically developed through soft law mechanisms, could provide practical guidance for states and private actors while remaining flexible enough to accommodate the rapidly evolving nature of the NewSpace sector. Institutions such as the UNCOPUOS and the IADC are particularly well-positioned to lead this effort. Both bodies have already demonstrated their capacity to shape international norms through instruments such as the UNCOPUOS Long-Term Sustainability Guidelines and the IADC Space Debris Mitigation Guidelines, which have significantly influenced national regulatory practices despite their non-binding character.

Building upon these existing initiatives, similar guidelines addressing extraterrestrial EIAs could establish common principles for evaluating the environmental consequences of space missions, including risks of contamination, resource disruption, and long-term impacts on the orbital and planetary environment. Although such standards would initially take the form of soft law, they could gradually influence national licensing regimes as states incorporate them into domestic space legislation and authorisation procedures. In doing so, they would contribute to the emergence of more harmonised international practices governing the environmental sustainability of space activities. For NewSpace companies, this would facilitate better access to global capital markets by demonstrating alignment with sustainability expectations, thereby fostering a more responsible, competitive, and future-proof space industry.